

Is there place for perfectionism in the NIR spectral data reduction?

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Context

- Near-infrared spectroscopy became crucially important in nearly all areas of modern observational astronomy, from Solar system bodies to the most distant galaxies
- Most major telescopes have NIR spectrographs and more will come on ELTs; however, NIR data reduction remains very challenging
- I will describe two “limiting” cases:
 - high signal-to-noise Echelle spectroscopy of stars
 - low resolution spectroscopy of very faint targets

NIR domain: know your enemies

- Detectors: modern CMOS HgCdTe detectors (H2RG) compare well to 20yrs old CCDs by cosmetics, read-out noise, dark current and have extra “surprises” (persistence, pix-to-pix sensitivity, non-linearity, ITAR restrictions, ...)
- Telescope/spectrograph emit thermal IR noticeable at wavelengths $>2\mu\text{m}$ and it may become a problem in the *K* band
- Earth atmosphere a.k.a. your main headache
 - some (powerful) people claim that ground-based NIR spectroscopy has no future at all

NIR Sky: emission and absorption

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- Both, airglow lines and absorption bands are highly variable in time and space (airmass)
 - They vary depending on ambient conditions as well: humidity, temperature and air pressure
- As consequences
 - NIR imaging requires sky background observations obtained near science fields (time + spatial)
 - NIR spectroscopy requires observations of telluric standards to correct for absorption

FIRE Spectrograph @Magellan Baade

- R=4000-6500 Echelle cross-dispersion spectroscopy with a 7'' long slit at $0.83 < \lambda < 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (+long slit low-res)
 - 4 cross-dispersing prisms (ZnSe + infrasil)
- Hawaii-2RG detector (2k*2k)
- Permanently mounted in the folded port

Las Campanas Stellar Library

- Stellar libraries are fundamental tools required to model stellar populations and study stellar atmospheres
 - Theoretical vs empirical: incomplete line lists vs small samples
 - Optical: several libraries containing 800+ stars (R=2300-40000)
 - NIR (full NIR domain): IRTF library (200 stars, R=2000) and X-Shooter Spectral Library (250 stars published, R=10000)
- Our goal: the most advanced stellar library in the NIR
 - 1200+ stars, extensive coverage of AGB stars, non-solar abundance patterns (Galactic bulge, LMC, SMC)
 - R=6500, complete NIR (0.8 to 2.5 μ m) using ***FIRE@Magellan***
 - High level of data homogeneity, S/N ratio 150-400:
 - Custom telescope control scripts
 - Dedicated FIRE Bright Source pipeline

LCO SL: Observations

- Observed as of Dec/2016: **1070** stars (**960** targets + 110 telluric stds)
 - Spectral types: WR, O to M9, sub-dwarfs to super-giants
 - 250 AGB stars (late M, C-R-S), the largest sample up-to-date
 - 20 LMC, 15 SMC, 40 bulge stars
- Observational strategy: scanning across the slit (see poster by K.Boutsia et al.)
 - eliminates seeing effects / slit losses and allows us to observe bright stars ($J=0$ mag)
 - a specific day-time calibration plan
 - arc/flats at different telescope/rotator positions
 - 10-12% of telluric standard stars

FIRE Bright Source Pipeline

- Goals:
 - Homogeneous data:
 - consistent spectral resolution ($R=6500$, $\sigma=20\text{km/s}$)
 - wavelength calibration better than 2km/s
 - Flux uncertainty:
 - $<3\%$ in z-K bands overall
 - $<0.5\%$ in 200nm windows
 - Telluric correction:
 - better than 2% correction quality for transmission $>50\%$

Problem #1: detector and flexures

- Detector:
 - 4 amplifiers with slightly different properties
 - Strong pixel-to-pixel sensitivity variations (standard for H2RG)
 - Many hot/warm/dead pixels
 - Substantial non-linearity (10% close to saturation)
- Instrument:
 - Slit position is not repeatable
 - Rotator and telescope positions dependent flexures up to 3 pixels
- SOLUTIONS:
 - calibrate the non-linearity using up-the-ramp flat fields
 - build bad pixel lists
 - do not change the slit between calibrations and science observations
 - create a “super-flat” to correct pixel-to-pixel sensitivity variations
 - we can apply arbitrary transformations to flat/arc frames to compensate flexures which is impossible otherwise

Problem #2: wavelength calibration

- ThAr has very few lines in the 2 red orders ($\lambda > 1.8\mu\text{m}$)
- OH lines are weak at ($\lambda < 1.5\mu\text{m}$); t_{exp} vary between 20 to 600s
 - **SOLUTION:** use them together; ThAr first; OH+water later on
- Cross disperser has 6(!) prisms (4 physical prisms)
 - 3D polynomial: 6(along disp.)*9(across disp.)*1(along the slit)
- **Precision: about 10 km/s (problems in the red)**

ThAr: 120sec

OH+H2O: 2*20sec

Problem #3: extraction and merging

- PSF across the slit:
 - often non-Gaussian: in short exposures (<1 sec) we see speckles
 - PSF is wavelength dependent: up-to 30% difference in width (z to K)
 - A and B traces might overlap and do not have the same shape/width
 - PSF might be cut by the slit on one end
- tiny sub-pix offsets between flat field and science frames:
 - flux changes by ~3-4% in one order: the order merging is affected

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- SOLUTIONS:
 - define an empirical PSF in one of the red orders (1.8 or 2.1 μm)
 - fit a PSF at every wavelength as an empirical one convolved with a Gaussian; allow for offsets along the slit to account for atm.dispersion
 - perform optimal extraction
 - derive the optimal offset between flat and science frames by minimizing the difference in the extracted signal where orders overlap

Problem #4: telluric correction / flux

- The telluric correction is tough:
 - residual wavelength calibration errors
 - spectral resolution changes within each order by ~10-15%
 - we do not observe telluric standards for every target; 1 every 10-12
 - telluric standards are never “standards”: stellar rotation, emission lines, mismatch of real/model stellar atmosphere parameters, etc.
 - PSF might be cut by the slit on one end
- Broadband flux calibration is subject to:
 - flat field lamp stability (not a problem as it turned out)
 - atmospheric extinction at the time of observation
- **SOLUTIONS:**
 - two-step telluric correction procedure (without a telluric star!)
 - a model containing a stellar atmosphere, an atmospheric transmission, the line-spread-function, and residual wavelength shifts is fitted into an observed spectrum
 - the whole reduction is re-done from the extraction step using the adjusted wavelength solution (precision better than 2km/s)
 - use 2MASS photometry for non-variable stars and measure the extinction trend during the night; apply it to all observed stars

Problem #4: telluric correction / flux

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FIRE Spectra: some examples

- When all problems described above have been properly solved, then...

MMT and Magellan IR Spectrograph

McLeod et al. 2012 PASP 124 1318

MMIRS

MMIRS Basic Capabilities

- YJHK imaging over 7x7 arcmin field of view
- Longslit spectroscopy with 7 arcmin slit
- Multiobject spectroscopy over 4x7 arcmin
- Design conceptually based on University of Florida FLAMINGOS and FLAMINGOS2
 - Optical design by H.Epps and D.Fabricant
- Spectroscopic data reduction pipeline
 - Chilingarian et al. 2015 PASP 127 406

Spectroscopic Capabilities

SPECTROSCOPIC MODES

Wavelength range	Disperser	Order	Filter	Pixels/spectrum	Resolution
0.96–1.07	<i>HK</i>	2	<i>Y</i>	360	1600
0.96–1.07	<i>J</i>	1	<i>Y</i>	520	2400
0.96–1.07	<i>H</i>	2	<i>Y</i>	670	3000
0.95–1.50	<i>HK</i>	1 + 2	<i>zJ</i>	var	800,1600
0.94–1.51	<i>J</i>	1	<i>zJ</i>	2600	2400
1.17–1.33	<i>J</i>	1	<i>J</i>	720	2800
1.25–2.45	<i>HK</i>	1	<i>HK</i>	1800	1400
1.50–1.79	<i>H</i>	1	<i>H</i>	800	2400
1.50–1.79	<i>H</i> (VPH)	1	<i>H</i>		3000
1.98–2.32	<i>HK</i>	1	<i>K</i>	550	1700
1.95–2.45	<i>K</i> (VPH)	1	<i>K_{spec}</i>		3000

Currently supported by the data reduction pipeline

DISPERSERS

Band	Lines mm ⁻¹	Prism angle in	Prism angle out	Prism material
<i>J</i> (ruled)	210	0°	20.1°	Infrasil
<i>H</i> (ruled)	150	9.2°	26.7°	Infrasil
<i>HK</i> (ruled)	81.6	9.2°	26.7°	Infrasil
<i>H</i> (VPH)	290	9.5°	9.5°	ZnSe ^a
<i>K</i> (VPH)	200	8.8°	8.8°	ZnSe ^a

^a VPH gratings use a pair of identical prisms.

MMIRS Observing Protocols

- Spectroscopy (long-slit and multi-object)
 - 2 or 4 dithering positions to facilitate sky subtraction
 - Typical exposure time: 300 sec, ramp=5sec
 - Mask alignment check every 2h (typical overhead: 2min)
 - Night time arcs and internal flats
 - Typical overhead: 3-4 min (before every alignment check)
 - Night time telluric standards
 - In 5 slits (center, left, right, top bottom)
 - Typical overhead: 10-15min
 - Day time darks
 - Data reduction: IDL based pipeline

MMIRS Data Reduction-1

Raw frame

Dark subtracted

Primary Reduction

1. Up-the-ramp fitting, non-linearity correction
2. Dark subtraction
3. Distortion mapping

MMIRS Data Reduction-2

Flat-Fielding and 2D Slit Extraction

MMIRS Data Reduction-3

Wavelength Calibration

1. Per-slit (from Ar spectrum)
2. Refining using slit positions
3. Adjusting using sky lines

MMIRS Data Reduction-4

Sky subtraction

Modified Kelson (2003) technique

NIR Sky Subtraction-1

- Classical technique in NIR:
 - Use of subtracted dithered pairs (or 4 frames)
 - Sky background (lines and not only) varies in time
 - Dealing with 4 frames requires to shift images along the slit and causes artefacts if slit images are distorted
- Modern technique (Kelson 2003, optical):
 - Using wavelength solution on non-linearised frames to create an oversampled sky vector
 - Create a model by parametrizing it using b -splines
 - Evaluate the model for every position on the slit

NIR Sky Subtraction-2

- An oversampled sky vector created using the Kelson (2003) technique on a single frame

NIR Sky Subtraction-3

- Why the original technique will not work:
 - In the MOS mode the slitlets are too short, and their images are too straight, so it is impossible to create a well sampled sky vector from a single slit
 - There are still some residual flat fielding errors. Low but sufficient to spoil the results
- Solution
 - Apply the algorithm on difference images
 - Create a sky model from all slitlets using X and Y positions as additional parameters
 - *b*-spline coefficients slightly vary across the field

NIR Sky Subtraction: what we get

MMIRS Data Reduction-5

- Rectification and Linearisation

Example of a Reduced Dataset

Program by R.Leiton and E.Daddi

Example of a Reduced Dataset

Example of an extracted spectrum

- A high-redshift narrow line AGN
 - 7h20min with 6.5m Magellan Clay, $m_H=19.8$, $z=1.54$
 - $S/N = 10$ in continuum; $R=1200$; 1" wide slit

A more extreme example

- A high-redshift ($z=7$) galaxy candidate
 - 20h with 6.5m Magellan Clay, $m_{J,AB}=24.5$
 - $S/N = 7$ in continuum in J; $R=2100$; 0.5" wide slit
 - *not a galaxy*: a T7 brown dwarf some 1kpc away

Summary

- Is perfect NIR data reduction possible? YES
 - high signal-to-noise targets are challenging
 - very faint targets are even more challenging
- What is needed for perfect data reduction?
 - know your detector
 - know your instrument
 - take all necessary calibrations: day and night time
 - think through all data reduction steps thoroughly

- Reference Catalog of galaxy SEDs: 800,000 galaxies
- Great discovery potential (e.g. [2015Sci...348..418C](#))
- Easy-to-use and feature rich website:
 - Google like queries
 - Interactive diagrams
 - Tutorials
- Has everything you need about galaxies in one place:
 - UV-to-NIR SEDs (k-corrected, of course)
 - Stellar masses
 - Stellar Ages and Metallicities
 - Morphologies
 - Emission lines: gas-phase metallicities; SFRs

